

Agroecology for Europe (AE4EU)

Towards the development of agroecology in Europe

Deliverable D.6.3 – First communication materials on agroecology

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Grant Agreement Number	101000478
Project acronym and title	AE4EU - Agroecology for Europe
Project website	www.ae4eu.eu
Funding Scheme	Coordination and support action (CSA)
Call identifier	H2020-FNR-2020-1
Topic	FNR-01-2020 Strengthening the European agro-ecological research and innovation ecosystem
Start date of project	January 1st, 2021
Duration	36 months
Project coordinator & organisation	Alexander Wezel - ISARA, Lyon, France
Lead Partner for deliverable	AEEU
Work package	WP6
Due date of deliverable	30/06/2022
Dissemination level	Public

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AE4EU

Executive summary

One of the AE4EU project aims is to raise awareness and discussion around agroecology. For this, the project developed a strategy of communication, dissemination and exploitation of its results for different target audience, from policymakers to agroecological living labs and initiatives. To reach this diverse audience, a variety of communication channels were defined and developed and will be used to support and ensure a proper dissemination of results and outcomes.

Some first materials were already released after the first half of the project: website articles, AE4EU Twitter and YouTube channel, 1 press release, 3 newsletters, 2 recorded webinars, 3 short videos with project partners and 1 short video with a stakeholder. The project was present at different public conferences that were used to share information about the project and its outcomes. During the 3rd Agroecology Europe Forum in 2021, a project poster was shared and a workshop on Living Labs was hosted. The recording was shared on the project partner's YouTube channel and on the AE4EU website.

1. Introduction

Task 6.3 aims at raising awareness of the capacity of agroecology to address global challenges, broaden engagement and enhance the connection between stakeholders to allow transition towards more sustainable agriculture and food systems in Europe. This will be done in parallel of a strong involvement of agroecology partners in the partnership dynamic mainly through the SCAR-Agroecology task force and the design of SRIA (Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda) for the EU agroecology partnership.

For AE4EU, communication, dissemination and exploitation of project's results are key objectives. Therefore, communication and dissemination is envisioned to take place in all WPs and throughout all phases of project development and implementation.

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2. AE4EU communication and dissemination strategy

2.1. Aims

In alignment with the project objectives, the primary goals for communication and dissemination are:

- To communicate and disseminate properly results, outputs and methodologies developed within the project to targeted stakeholders
- To collect feedback from scientific communities, agricultural stakeholders, value chain actors, policymakers, consumers and civil society regarding the development of agroecology in Europe in link with the European partnership on agroecology living labs (LLs) and research infrastructures (RIs)
- To connect and enhance collaboration within and between agroecological LL and RI and allow knowledge creation and knowledge exchange
- To promote and publish scientific information concerning project results
- To provide recommendations to policymakers for improved policies as well as recommendations to public and private funders in the light of the partnership on agroecology LLs and RIs and other future funding for programmes or projects related to agroecology
- To provide pilot trainings to different farmer groups.
- To facilitate and reinforce a European Agroecology Exchange Network and develop a Knowledge Hub

More generally, the aim is to ensure that project results and messages are delivered effectively to a diversity of stakeholders and end users within and outside the project consortium at different scales:

regional, EU and global scales. Actors such as agroecological initiatives in general are seen as both target audiences and multipliers to wider audiences.

2.2. Target groups of AE4EU communication and dissemination

Depending on the target group, different communication and dissemination messages were developed and started to be transported via appropriate channels and media. The most important target groups for agroecology in Europe are actors from the sectors of policy, policy decision makers at EU and national level, civil society and as well as from science. Actors such as research funding agencies, stakeholders in format of agroecology such as LLs or Living Territories as well as actors at the agricultural production end such as consumers are also highly relevant. A set of relevant actor groups related to Agroecology in Europe are presented below.

Table 1: Target groups of the AE4EU communication and dissemination strategy with related goals, messages transported, and channels used to reach them.

Target groups	Goal of the communication	Messages to be transported	Channels and productions of communication
EU Policy makers	To inform about findings from AE4EU link with the partnership	Current development and opportunities for agroecology in Europe. Specific insight to take into account in the partnership and SRIA design	Policy briefs, meetings, newsletters, webinars and workshop, videos
SCAR-Agroecology group	Share the findings of AE4EU at the light of the partnership	Current development and opportunities for agroecology in Europe. Specific insight to take into account in the partnership and SRIA design	AE4EU and ALL-Ready conference, Policy briefs, meetings, newsletters, webinars, website, workshops
Agroecology initiatives in Europe	Information regarding the dynamic around agroecology in Europe (partnership etc.) and share the findings of AE4EU	Current development and opportunities for agroecology in Europe. Enable the creation and strengthening of link among stakeholders	Academic posters and presentations at conferences, AE4EU and ALL-Ready conference, the knowledge Hub, newsletters, social media, webinars, website, workshops
Living labs practitioners and researchers	Strengthen an agroecological Living Lab community	Increase the knowledge of agroecological living labs	Academic Posters and presentations at conferences, AE4EU and ALL-Ready conference, meetings, the knowledge Hub, newsletters, social media, webinars, website, workshops
Scientific communities around agroecology and beyond	Share results and allow their dissemination and potential exploitation	Increase the general knowledge regarding the development of agroecology in European countries	Academic posters and presentations at conference, AE4EU and ALL-Ready conference, publication of academic papers and webinars
Farmers	Share results of AE4EU and allow their dissemination	Increase the general knowledge regarding the development of agroecology, create link with other agroecological initiatives and strengthen the network of stakeholder	Newsletters, the knowledge Hub, Training sessions, webinars, website, workshops
General public	Inform about AE4EU and agroecology	Inform about the project outcomes, agroecology concept and its potential to transform food systems	Project website, social media, newsletters
Journalist	Inform about AE4EU and agroecology development in Europe	Inform about the project outcomes, agroecology concept and its potential to transform food systems	Project website, social media, newsletters, press release
AE4EU partners and associated partners	Introduce and inform about the process and progress of the project		Printed and online information material, events, newsletters, meetings

3. Communication and dissemination channels

Different communication channels are used to enable a successful communication and dissemination of AE4EU results and outcomes to the different target groups (Table 1). To ensure a coherence in the overall AE4EU communication a visual identity of the project was developed at the beginning of it. Logo, branded templates and audio-visual materials (reports, PowerPoint presentations, posters, social media, newsletters), acknowledging also EU funding support were developed and disseminate among AE4EU partners. Content that needs to reach a broad or specific audience will be translated in different European languages to support the communication and dissemination of it.

A shared working plan – with a specific focus on communication and dissemination materials and events – was designed and shared between AE4EU partners, and is regularly updated.

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Figure 1: The logo of the AE4EU project.

3.1. AE4EU website

In month 5 the official website of AE4EU was launched. This website is the central point of the AE4EU communication and dissemination, gathering all the content and progress produced by the project. In the design of the AE4EU website¹, a specific page, dedicated to the understanding of agroecology and informing about the project progress and its outcomes has been built. The goal of this website is to disseminate and produce some materials to share the vision of agroecology from the AE4EU consortium perspective, make available some project results and outputs.

¹ www.ae4eu.eu

Figure 2: Screenshot from the AE4EU website – page “Agroecology in Europe”

The website dedicates a specific space to each WP and main outputs of the project (mapping – WP1, funding – WP3 and policies – WP5) and shares produced communication materials, allowing visitors to choose from a variety of content (reports, videos, and articles) that explain agroecology and project results in different ways. The country reports from the mapping will especially constitute an important release from the project, summarizing the state of agroecology in different European countries, according to different pillars: practice, education and training, living labs, movement, and science. The first two webinars on the results of the ‘Mapping of Agroecology in Austria and Germany’ and in Italy and Greece were made available on the website and on YouTube².

The core AE4EU communication team ensure the update of the website and generate the content with the active support of the AE4EU partners. For this, the monthly communication group meetings ensure a proper communication within the consortium to achieve this goal.

3.2. Articles and brochures

Among the different communication and dissemination format planned, brochures and academic articles will be delivered. For the moment, one academic article on the mapping of Austria and Germany is planned. Two further academic articles are also foreseen for the second period of the project. All those articles will be submitted to open access journals to favor a large dissemination and exploitation of results.

² https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v3el_4KI0YY

In addition, different brochures will be developed. A first brochure explaining the concept of agroecology to a wide audience is planned. The aim is to make agroecology easily understandable to a broad audience. It will be produced in English, but the aim is also to have it in several languages allowing better dissemination in different countries.

3.3. Conferences and forums

AE4EU partners already participate to different public event, including conferences such as TP Organic and TERRA Madre. Among them, different members of the consortium, through the lead of Agroecology Europe, participated actively to the 3rd Agroecology Europe Forum in November 2021 with the topic of ‘Agroecology to regenerate our food systems and communities and enhance biodiversity’.

During the Forum organised by one of the project partners, Agroecology Europe, a poster was shown to inform participants about the AE4EU project and exchange with them. With about 150 attending participants on-site in Barcelona, the AE4EU poster had a good exposure to a broad variety of stakeholders (social movements, academia, young people) from all over Europe. In addition, an online workshop on LLs was organised and led within the Forum by UNISG, an AE4EU partner. The video is available on the AE4EU website and is already uploaded on the Agroecology Europe YouTube³ channel. The two-and-a-half-hour webinar and workshop presented the AE4EU LLs in Italy, the UK and the Netherlands and facilitated exchange with stakeholders and organisations such as Rete Semi Rurali, Italy, and Merola Future Lab, Portugal.

During the discussion with the ALL-Ready H2020 consortium, a common idea and willingness to organise a common final project conference was discussed and agreed. This will be a major route for disseminating project results to multiple actor groups, allowing exchange of scientific and technical knowledge as well as delivery of practical outputs.

3.4. The knowledge Hub

Planned to be set online in a first version end of 2022, the agroecology Hub launched by AE4EU will become a significant part of the communication and dissemination strategy. To make the Hub attractive for stakeholders and use this opportunity to diffuse the results and outcome of the AE4EU project beyond its lifespan, materials of communication will be uploaded on it. It will also include material and information shared and uploaded by stakeholder. After the end of the project, Agroecology Europe take the charge of maintaining and updating the knowledge hub.

³ <https://youtu.be/ZrJOaRdPpbo>

3.5. Newsletters

With more than 350 registered persons, the newsletter of AE4EU already reach a large and diversified audience of actors in terms of background and countries. A newsletter is sent every six months to share the latest update and progress of the project to an interested community of stakeholders. To date, three newsletters were sent and are available on the AE4EU website⁴.

3.6. Policy briefs

According to the main goals of AE4EU, policy briefs are one of the key instruments and channels to ensure a proper communication and dissemination. For the moment two policy briefs^{5,6} were produced in February and July 2022. The first policy brief was disseminated following a workshop with policymakers in Brussels and disseminate to the SCAR-AE and related stakeholder groups. The second policy brief is for the moment only disseminate through the AE4EU website, but larger dissemination will follow.

Figure 3: First pages of the AE4EU newsletters

⁴ <https://www.ae4eu.eu/category/newsletters/>

⁵ <https://www.ae4eu.eu/ae4eu-policy-brief/>

⁶ <https://www.ae4eu.eu/policy-brief-10-steps-to-achieve-the-european-green-deal/>

3.7. Press release

In parallel of the project kick-off, a first press release⁷ was developed to inform of the launch of the project and share the vision of the consortium with a wide audience. To ensure a proper diffusion within the agroecology network in Europe, this press release was translated in three languages.

3.8. Social media

To favor dissemination of the project and be able to reach the targeted audience, two social media account on Twitter⁸ and Youtube⁹ were created. Launched in June 2021, the twitter account has now 254 followers and aim to have a weekly activity of publication.

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3.9. Videos

One of the aims of task 6.2. is also the production of easily accessible and understandable communication materials on agroecology and how it addresses global challenges. To do so, the production of short videos has been planned and started during the first in-person meeting in May 2022 in Lugo. These short videos interviews of representatives of AE4EU partners and external stakeholders aim to provide short explanations of the project and the understanding, expectations and hopes regarding agroecology from the project consortium perspective and the external stakeholders which participated in a workshop during the meeting. Besides the content on agroecology in a more general way, some videos explain more complex topics such as LLs and the EU agroecology partnerships. The videos will be shared on the AE4EU YouTube channel¹⁰, AE4EU website¹¹, and Twitter¹², as well as distributed by the project partners in their networks. To date, three videos of partners, one video of a member of the SCAR-AE group and the two videos of the mapping webinar were published. Further partner videos are available and will be published in the second half of 2022.

⁷ <https://www.ae4eu.eu/agroecology-europe-new-challenge/>

⁸ https://twitter.com/AE4EU_H2020

⁹ https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCOsUVqM8tOhE28Gr2xcp2_w

¹⁰ https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCOsUVqM8tOhE28Gr2xcp2_w

¹¹ <https://www.ae4eu.eu/fr/accueil/>

¹² https://twitter.com/AE4EU_H2020

Picture 4: Screenshot of youtube account of Agroecology for Europe

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Picture 5: Screenshot of the twitter account of Agroecology for Europe

3.10. Webinars and workshops

Two webinars were already achieved regarding the mapping of agroecology in Austria and Germany as well as Greece and Italy. Different workshops were organized internally and with external stakeholder for instance with policy maker in February and June (WP5 activity) and with the three AE4EU LLs in Italy, the Netherlands and in UK.

4. Next steps

Fostering the development of agroecology in Europe, in link with the development of the partnership is a key task of the AE4EU project. The current communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy should allow and ensure a coherent and efficient activity within the AE4EU consortium to reach out to different target groups and stakeholders. For the second half of the project, more effort is foreseen to increase further the communication and dissemination of the project results and achievements.